

SPEECH ACTS AND THE PRAGMATICS OF GENDERED IDENTITY IN MARLON JAMES' *THE BOOK OF NIGHT WOMEN*

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Abstract

Language functions as a performative force through which gendered and racial identities are constituted and contested, indicating that speech acts operate as both the instruments of domination and sites of resistance. This study examines how language constructs and shapes identity in Marlon James's *The Book of Night Women* through the lens of Judith Butler's extensions of speech act theory in *Excitable Speech* (1997) and *Gender Trouble* (1990). It explores how speech acts define the identities of enslaved Black women within the novel. Using a qualitative approach with purposive sampling, the analysis focuses on selected excerpts that demonstrate how words function as instruments of power—both in constructing identities and as a means of resistance. The study identifies how injurious speech, including racial and gendered insults, wounds characters and shapes their identities, while also highlighting moments of subversive resignification, where characters reclaim language as a tool for empowerment and self-definition. Through Butler's concept of performativity, the study shows how gendered and racial identities are performed and reproduced through everyday utterances, and how these same utterances can be strategically re-appropriated to challenge dominant hierarchies. The findings reveal that in *The Book of Night Women*, language operates simultaneously as a mechanism for constituting identity and a medium for resistance, demonstrating the complex relationship between speech acts and identity formation.

Keywords: identity, injurious speech, language, performativity, resignification.

Introduction

Identity is commonly understood as the constellation of characteristics through which an individual or group becomes recognisable and distinct (McKinlay, 2010; Kouhpaenejad & Gholaminejad, 2013). In literary studies, identity is not treated as a stable or essential attribute but as a complex and evolving construct shaped by

personal experience, social relations, cultural affiliations, and discursive practices (Bucholtz & Hall, 2005; Hansen & Milburn, 2015). Literary texts often represent identity as fluid and contested, with characters negotiating their sense of self in response to internal conflicts and external pressures imposed by social structures and power relations.

The question of identity has long occupied a central place in scholarship on slavery and postcolonial literature. Under the transatlantic slave system, enslavement entailed not only physical captivity but also the systematic dismantling and reconstruction of personhood. Enslaved Africans were frequently stripped of names, kinship ties, languages, and cultural markers and compelled to assume identities imposed by colonial authority. For enslaved women, this process was intensified by the gendered dynamics of slavery, which exposed them to domestic labour, sexual exploitation, and patriarchal domination. As Thoker (2017) observes, “slavery did not only deny women their freedom but also constructed them as commodities, doubly oppressed by both patriarchy and slavery” (p. 299). Consequently, enslaved women’s identities were produced at the intersection of race, class, and gender oppression, rendering them particularly vulnerable within systems of domination.

Marlon James’s *The Book of Night Women* (2009) revisits this historical reality through its depiction of enslaved women living on a Jamaican sugar plantation in the late eighteenth century. The novel centres on Lilith, a girl born into slavery whose perceived dark power inspires both fear and reverence among the women around her. As she matures, Lilith becomes entangled with the Night Women, a secret collective of enslaved women plotting a rebellion against plantation authority. While the group regards her as pivotal to their revolutionary aims, Lilith’s growing emotional awareness and emerging sense of self lead her to challenge the restrictive identities imposed on enslaved women, ultimately destabilising the revolt she is expected to advance. Through characters such as Lilith and Homer, the novel foregrounds the struggle of enslaved women to negotiate identity within a violently oppressive social order that persistently seeks to define and limit them (Ozuna, 2017). By focusing on female perspectives, James disrupts dominant slave narratives that have often privileged male experiences and highlights how women navigate the performative demands of slavery through obedience, silence, and sexual availability while simultaneously cultivating spaces of solidarity and resistance through secrecy and subversive action.

This study draws on Judith Butler’s theories of gender performativity (1990) and injurious speech and resignification (1997) as a critical framework for analysing these nuances of identity formation. Butler conceptualises identity not as a fixed essence but as the effect of repeated acts and discursive practices that produce the illusion of stability (McKinlay, 2010). Crucially, these same practices also contain

the potential for disruption and reworking. Applying Butler's framework to *The Book of Night Women* allows for a critical examination of how enslaved women's identities are constituted through both performative behaviour and linguistic practices, as well as how these identities may be destabilised and reconstituted through acts of resignification and resistance.

Although existing scholarship on *The Book of Night Women* has examined themes of slavery, violence, race, gender, and resistance, (Nehl, 2016;; Ozuna,2017; Thoker, 2017; Shafti, 2024) comparatively little attention has been paid to the ways identity is specifically constructed and contested through language and performativity in the novel. This study addresses this gap by analysing the text through Butler's theoretical interventions in *Gender Trouble* (1990) and *Excitable Speech* (1997), with particular emphasis on gender performativity, injurious speech, and subversive resignification. By doing so, it explores how enslaved women's identities are produced, regulated, and potentially reconstituted within the discursive constraints of plantation society. The construction of identity under slavery remains a critical concern in literary and cultural studies, particularly given the ways enslaved subjects were denied individuality and reduced to property defined by race and subjugation. For enslaved women, identity was further complicated by the convergence of gender oppression and sexual exploitation. While literary representations have long grappled with these tensions, some critical approaches risk treating identity as fixed or essentialised. There is therefore a need for theoretical frameworks that foreground the instability, contestation, and reconstitution of identity within oppressive systems, a need to which Butler's work is particularly responsive.

The main aim of this study is to examine how language constructs identity in Marlon James's *The Book of Night Women* through the lens of Judith Butler's theories of performativity and resignification. To achieve this aim, the study pursues the following objectives:

- i. to analyse how gender performativity operates in the novel, particularly in the ways enslaved women enact and subvert prescribed roles on the plantation;
- ii. to examine the role of injurious speech in constituting the identities of enslaved women;
- iii. to investigate instances of subversive resignification in the novel, where imposed identities are reworked and contested. In pursuit of the above objectives, this study contributes to scholarship on Marlon James by offering a sustained Butlerian reading of *The Book of Night Women* because even though the novel has attracted critical attention for its engagement with slavery, resistance, and gender, it has not been extensively examined

through the specific theoretical insights offered by Judith Butler. By applying the concepts of gender performativity, injurious speech, and resignification, the study deepens understanding of how enslaved women's identities are discursively constituted and reworked within the text.

of identity formation and contestation in James's novel.

Literature Review

This chapter reviews existing scholarship relevant to the present study. It surveys critical works on Marlon James's *The Book of Night Women*, with particular attention to scholarly engagements with race, gender, violence, and resistance in the novel, as well as studies that examine Judith Butler's theoretical contributions, especially gender performativity, injurious speech, and subversive resignification. Together, these bodies of literature establish the conceptual and critical context within which the present analysis is situated.

In "Violent Liaisons: Historical Crossings and the Negotiation of Sex, Sexuality, and Race in *The Book of Night Women* and *The True History of Paradise*," Vásquez (2012) examines how sexual relationships in James's novel expose the intersections of racial power and identity performance. Vásquez argues that the character Lilith occupies a liminal position—both Black and light-skinned, oppressed yet intermittently empowered—within the plantation hierarchy. Drawing on postcolonial and feminist frameworks, the study employs the concept of "sexual economies" to interrogate how colonial violence and racial hierarchies are negotiated through sexual relations and the enslaved female body. Vásquez's analysis demonstrates that sexual encounters in *The Book of Night Women* function as narrative devices through which desire, coercion, and resistance intersect, refiguring the enslaved woman's body as a site of both trauma and agency. By foregrounding Lilith's ambiguous positioning as both victim and agent, the study reveals how James exposes the enduring effects of racial and sexual domination while allowing for moments of subversive redefinition.

While Vásquez (2012) acknowledges the performative dimensions of identity, the emphasis remains on corporeality and sexual interaction as narrative mechanisms. The present study departs from this focus by shifting attention from bodily performance to linguistic performativity. Drawing on Judith Butler's *Excitable Speech*, it argues that speech acts such as naming, insult, command, silence, and refusal are central to the construction and regulation of identity in the novel. Thus, whereas Vásquez explores desire as performance, this study foregrounds language as a constitutive force in identity formation.

Thoker's (2017) "A Postcolonial Feminist Approach to Marlon James' *The Book of Night Women*" examines the intersections of race, gender, and colonial domination

in the novel, focusing on the double colonisation of Black women by white supremacy and patriarchy. Grounded in postcolonial feminist theory and drawing on scholars such as Gayatri Spivak and Chandra Talpade Mohanty, Thoker analyses how James reconstructs the history of Jamaican slavery from the perspective of enslaved women. The study argues that the novel presents female slave experience not solely as racial subjugation but also as a site of resistance, agency, and voice. Thoker finds that James employs narrative strategies such as multiple perspectives and creolised language to challenge Eurocentric historiography, enabling enslaved women to reclaim subjectivity from the margins. Through Lilith's evolving consciousness, the study identifies a subversive feminist discourse that contests both colonial authority and patriarchal dominance within the slave community. However, while Thoker (2017) addresses the notion of "voice" thematically, his analysis does not examine speech acts themselves or the ways in which utterances, silences, commands, and naming practices operate performatively to shape identity and power relations. The present study extends this discussion by moving from representation to performativity, employing Butler's concepts of injurious speech and resignification to analyse how language itself functions as a performative mechanism in *The Book of Night Women*.

In "Untangling the Threads of Folklore: An Analysis of Marlon James's Novels through the Lens of Henry Bourne's *Antiquitates Vulgares*," Shafti (2024) explores James's novels *The Book of Night Women*, *The Brief History of Seven Killings*, and *Black Leopard, Red Wolf*, focusing on the integration of African and Jamaican folklore. Using Bourne's *Antiquitates Vulgares* as a comparative framework, the study demonstrates how James weaves folk beliefs, rituals, supernatural elements, and oral traditions into his narratives to reflect themes of identity, resistance, and empowerment. Shafti argues that folklore functions as cultural memory and as a counter-discursive tool against colonial oppression. The study further finds that James's use of folk language and oral idioms serves a dual purpose: preserving indigenous cultural memory while unsettling colonial linguistic hierarchies. By linking Bourne's eighteenth-century reflections on "vulgar antiquities" with James's reanimation of African diasporic myth, Shafti shows how folklore becomes a site of both remembrance and resistance.

This study differs from the present research in scope and focus. While Shafti (2024) examines folklore, ritual, and myth across multiple texts using a comparative framework, the current research undertakes a close textual analysis of *The Book of Night Women* with specific attention to how repeated speech acts contribute to the construction of character identity.

Nehl's (2016) chapter, "A Vicious Circle of Violence: Revisiting Jamaican Slavery in Marlon James' *The Book of Night Women*," offers a historically grounded examination of violence in the novel through the lenses of Black feminist thought,

postcolonial theory, and trauma studies. Nehl situates the text within the tradition of neo-slave narratives and argues that the novel depicts a cyclical structure of violence in which enslaved people are trapped within systems of oppression and counter-violence. Drawing on scholars such as Saidiya Hartman and Frantz Fanon, Nehl demonstrates how James's portrayal of sexual and intra-Black violence exposes the psychological devastation of slavery and the moral ambiguity surrounding resistance. A central aspect of Nehl's critique concerns the ethics of representation, particularly the depiction of Black women's bodies. He contends that the novel's graphic representations of sexual violence risk aestheticising trauma and reproducing spectacle. Drawing on feminist scholars such as Angela Davis and Deborah McDowell, Nehl argues that James does not always provide sufficient ethical reflexivity in representing sexual violence. While Nehl's analysis offers an important critique of bodily and psychological violence, it differs from the present study in focus. Whereas Nehl foregrounds trauma and ethical representation, this research turns to the politics of speech, examining how language functions as an injurious and identity-forming act within the plantation system. By drawing on Butler's *Excitable Speech* and *Gender Trouble*, the study adds a linguistic-performative dimension to existing scholarship.

Ozuna's (2017) "Feminine Power: Women Contesting Plantocracy in *The Book of Night Women*" examines how enslaved and marginalised women assert power within the plantation order through both overt rebellion and covert resistance. Ozuna highlights the collective strength of women such as Homer, Nanni, and Lilith, arguing that their resistance extends beyond physical revolt to include caregiving, domestic labour, ritual, and secret organisation. She posits that femininity itself becomes a site of rebellion and that women construct alternative power structures rooted in memory, bonding, and ritual practice. While Ozuna's analysis provides valuable insights into communal resistance, it does not examine the discursive strategies through which such resistance is articulated. Butler's framework, by contrast, reveals how power is not only embodied but also spoken into being.

Schwartz's (2021) study, "True Darkness and True Womanness: A Study of Sisterhood in Marlon James' *The Book of Night Women*," offers a feminist analysis of female solidarity and resistance in the novel. Drawing on Black feminist theory and scholars such as Audre Lorde and bell hooks, Schwartz argues that the Night Women embody a radical form of sisterhood that transforms collective suffering into empowerment. The study demonstrates how secrecy, shared resistance, and storytelling function as strategies of survival and rebellion. While Schwartz foregrounds the emotional and communal dimensions of identity formation, the present study diverges by focusing on the linguistic and performative dimensions

of identity. Rather than analysing sisterhood as a narrative theme, this research examines how speech itself operates as a mechanism for constituting identity.

Cox's (2023) article, "Self-Critical Freedoms: White Women, Intersectionality and *Excitable Speech*," offers a critical interrogation of Butler's theory of injurious speech through the lens of intersectionality and Black feminist critique. Cox argues that *Excitable Speech* insufficiently accounts for the lived experiences of Black women and cautions against celebratory readings of resignification. Drawing on Kimberlé Crenshaw, Cox contends that the resignification of slurs may reproduce patriarchal and racial violence, particularly when misogynoir remains unacknowledged. This critique is directly relevant to the present study, which applies Butler's framework to a literary text centred on enslaved Black women. Unlike Cox's primarily theoretical engagement, however, the present study applies Butler's ideas to a sustained literary analysis, grounding them in the historical and linguistic realities of enslavement.

Rothenberg's (2006) "Embodied Political Performativity: Butler's Theory of the Performative in the Context of Politics" expands Butler's concept of performativity beyond language to include bodily presence and political action. Rothenberg traces Butler's intellectual development from *Gender Trouble* (1990) to *Excitable Speech* (1997), arguing that political performativity emerges through the convergence of speech, gesture, and vulnerability in public spaces. While Rothenberg's analysis focuses on contemporary political protest, the present study addresses a markedly different context: the plantation society of *The Book of Night Women*, where speech and bodily action occur under coercive and life-threatening conditions. Performativity in this context must therefore be read through the lens of survival rather than voluntary political expression.

Finally, Chambers (2007), in "Giving Accounts of Injurious Speech: Critical Reflections on Judith Butler," offers a philosophical critique of Butler's claims regarding resignification. Chambers argues that Butler may underestimate the structural entrenchment of power relations that limit the transformative potential of linguistic resistance. While acknowledging the conceptual strength of Butler's theory, he cautions against assuming that reclaiming language necessarily results in empowerment. This critique informs the present study by foregrounding the limitations of resignification within rigid hierarchies of race, gender, and class. However, whereas Chambers engages Butler at a theoretical level, the current research applies her framework to a specific literary text, using the voices of enslaved women to examine how injurious speech and performativity operate within a historically grounded system of domination.

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded in Speech Act Theory as originally formulated by J. L. Austin (1962), with its analytical focus shaped by Judith Butler's extension of the theory in *Gender Trouble* (1990) and *Excitable Speech: A Politics of the Performative* (1997). Speech Act Theory, situated within the philosophy of language and linguistics, posits that language does not merely describe reality but actively performs actions. Utterances such as requests, commands, promises, and apologies do not simply convey information; they constitute social acts performed through language.

Austin (1962) introduces the distinction between constative utterances, which describe states of affairs and may be evaluated as true or false, and performative utterances, which bring about an action in the act of being spoken. His foundational examples of performatives include "I do" (uttered during a marriage ceremony), "I name this ship the Queen Elizabeth," "I give and bequeath my watch to my brother," and "I bet you sixpence it will rain tomorrow" (Austin, 1962, p. 5). Unlike constatives, performatives are evaluated not in terms of truth-value but according to whether they succeed or fail. This success depends on what Austin terms felicity conditions, that is, the conventional and contextual requirements that must be fulfilled for an utterance to function effectively as an action. Austin further distinguishes between three interrelated dimensions of speech acts: the locutionary act, referring to the production of a meaningful linguistic expression; the illocutionary act, which concerns the intended social function of the utterance (such as commanding, promising, or warning); and the perlocutionary act, which refers to the effects an utterance has on its audience, such as persuading, intimidating, or compelling action. These distinctions underscore the idea that meaning is not exhausted by linguistic form alone but is inseparable from intention, context, and social effect.

Building on Austin's work, Searle (1969) systematises Speech Act Theory by developing a taxonomy of illocutionary acts, which he classifies into five categories: representatives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declarations. Searle also introduces the notion of constitutive rules, which do not merely regulate behaviour but create the very possibility of certain actions. He formulates these rules as "X counts as Y in context C" (Searle, 1969, p. 33), emphasising that speech acts derive their force from socially recognised conventions. Additionally, Searle elaborates on felicity conditions, including sincerity and essential conditions, and places particular emphasis on speaker intention, arguing that the meaning of a speech act is inseparable from the intentions that animate it.

Judith Butler extends Speech Act Theory beyond its traditional linguistic and philosophical applications into the domain of identity formation. In *Gender Trouble*

(1990) and *Excitable Speech* (1997), Butler argues that identity, particularly gender and subjectivity, is not a pre-given essence but is constituted through repeated speech acts and embodied practices that are regulated by social norms and power relations. For Butler, identity is not something one *is* but something one *does*, repeatedly, through discursive and corporeal acts. Language thus becomes a mechanism not only of communication but also of regulation, exclusion, and control. A central concept in Butler's work is linguistic vulnerability, which arises from the fact that subjects are constituted in and through language prior to any conscious agency. According to Butler (1997), individuals are vulnerable to language because language precedes them and shapes the conditions under which they become intelligible as subjects. Injurious speech such as racial slurs, hate speech, or degrading naming practices derives its power from this vulnerability. Butler demonstrates, through her critique of U.S. Supreme Court rulings, that legal attempts to regulate injurious speech often re-inscribe the violence they seek to contain, as legal discourse may displace the suffering of marginalised subjects while re-centering dominant perspectives.

Butler (1997) further argues that the force of injurious speech does not stem from a single utterance or speaker but from the repetition of historically sedimented norms. Because such speech draws its authority from past usages, its injurious power cannot be easily located in individual intention alone. As a result, Butler concludes that while words do wound, their capacity to injure is embedded in broader discursive histories, making purely legal remedies insufficient and necessitating political and critical intervention. Closely related to injurious speech is Butler's concept of subversive resignification, which refers to the possibility that harmful words may be re-appropriated and recontextualised by marginalised groups. Butler (1997) illustrates this process with reference to the reclamation of racial slurs. While the historical violence of such terms is not erased, their repetition in new contexts may disrupt dominant meanings and generate alternative forms of solidarity or resistance. Resignification thus reveals that language is never fully controllable and always carries the potential for unintended or counter-hegemonic effects.

In *Gender Trouble* (1990), Butler further develops the notion of performativity by arguing that gender operates in a manner analogous to performative utterances. Drawing on Austin's distinction between constatives and performatives, Butler contends that gender does not express a prior identity but actively produces identity through repeated, socially regulated acts. Gestures, styles of speech, bodily movements, and modes of dress function as performative acts that create the illusion of a stable gender identity. These acts are not manifestations of an inner essence but are reiterated practices through which gender becomes intelligible within a given cultural framework. Butler's critical intervention lies in her

rethinking of the politics of performativity. While identity is produced through repetition within regulatory norms, this very repetition also opens up possibilities for disruption and resistance. Speech is therefore “excitable”: it is always implicated in power relations and always capable of producing effects that exceed or unsettle dominant intentions.

This theoretical framework informs the analysis of Marlon James’s *The Book of Night Women* by foregrounding language as a constitutive force in the formation of identity. Drawing on Butler’s *Gender Trouble* (1990) and *Excitable Speech* (1997), the study examines how gender and subjectivity in the novel are produced through repeated speech acts shaped by racial, sexual, and colonial power structures. The framework is applied through close textual analysis of selected scenes and character interactions, focusing on injurious speech (including racial and sexual slurs and naming practices), gender performativity, and instances of subversive resignification. In doing so, the study demonstrates how identity in the novel is not merely represented but actively constituted and contested through language.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research design and an analytical approach to examine the relationship between language and identity in Marlon James’s *The Book of Night Women*. The research is text-based and interpretative, focusing on how identity, particularly gendered subjectivity, is constituted, regulated, and contested through language within the novel. The analysis is structured around three thematic categories: Gender Performativity in *The Book of Night Women*, Injurious Speech and the Power of Language, and Subversive Resignification and Resistance. The study draws specifically on Judith Butler’s extension of Speech Act Theory as articulated in *Gender Trouble* (1990) and *Excitable Speech: A Politics of the Performative* (1997). Butler’s theoretical framework serves as the primary analytical tool for examining how language functions not only as a medium of communication but also as a performative mechanism that produces identity, enforces subjection, and enables resistance. By foregrounding Butler’s concepts of gender performativity, injurious speech, linguistic vulnerability, and resignification, the study investigates how repeated speech acts operate within the power structures of slavery to shape the identities of enslaved women in the text.

The data used for the study are drawn exclusively from Marlon James’s *The Book of Night Women* (2009). The corpus consists of selected excerpts from the novel, including dialogue and narrative passages, which exemplify the use of language in constructing, constraining, or challenging identity. These excerpts include instances of naming practices, insults, commands, silences, and acts of verbal defiance. Attention is paid to both spoken and narrated discourse in order to capture how

characters are positioned within relations of power and how language mediates oppression and agency.

Purposive sampling is employed as the sampling technique for data selection. This approach is appropriate because the study does not seek to analyse the entire text exhaustively but rather focuses on passages that are particularly salient to the research objectives. The selected excerpts are deliberately chosen for their relevance to Butler's theoretical concepts, especially injurious speech, gender performativity, and subversive resignification. The analytical procedure involves close textual analysis of the selected excerpts. Verbal exchanges between characters are examined to identify how speech acts function at locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary levels in line with Butler's reworking of Speech Act Theory. Each excerpt is analysed in relation to the ways it enacts identity, reinforces domination, or opens up possibilities for resistance through resignification. This interpretative process enables the study to demonstrate how language in *The Book of Night Women* operates as a site where identity is both imposed and contested.

Data

The excerpts, which serve as the data for the study are presented in the tables below and categorised to reflect: Performativity, Injurious speech, and Subversive Resignification.

Table 1: Gender Performativity

EXCERPTS	DESCRIPTION
“She swing the club, clap the ball clear cross the field and make one run to all four base and beat the boys but couldn't understand when the wet nurse slap her and say that a good girl was supposed to make manchild win. Lilith cuss and ask if manchild can't win if girl don't lose and she get another slap.” (James, 2009, p.1)	This excerpt reflects how identity (especially gender) is enforced through language. Here, the wet nurse tells Lilith how she is to behave as a woman.
“As soon as she sees circe her mouth shut up and she couldn't do nothing but mumble . 'Speakup damn girl, circe say'. Lilith start cry. She couldn't say her cho-cho be bleeding. Circe would think she done nastiness for sure.	The phrase is not simply an order to talk; it is a performative act that asserts Circe's authority and pushes Lilith into a position of submission. It also shows how circe has taught Lilith to associate

<p>Some nastiness with boy that circe always saying that she born to do.” (James, 2009, p. 3)</p>	<p>her femininity with her sexual availability to men.</p>
<p>“ too spirited. She too spirited, that damn girl, say circe. He was just goin' cut her down a notch get rid of that damn pride. She is just a nigger girl'. What you say? 'she too spirited. Think she be some nigger queen. She too spirited she need a man to fix her, damn girl'”(James, 2009, p.11-12)</p>	<p>This a linguistic act of control. Here circe turns Lilith's liveliness and independency into a flaw. In this way, Circe’s language creates Lilith as a problem that must be corrected.</p>
<p>"Not long after that one of the house womens says she should be breeding, just like her mama" (James, 2009, p.4)</p>	<p>This excerpt shows gender performativity because it reveals how society expects Lilith to act according to fixed ideas of womanhood, in this case, being valued mainly for reproduction.</p>
<p>" Soon and very soon you goin' to be taking man, Circe say as she look out the window" (James, 2009, p.6</p>	<p>This words being repeated show how language is use construct Lilith's identity as a woman.</p>

Table 2: Injurious speech

EXCERPTS	DESCRIPTION
<p>"-wheh de fookin' gal deh - Hello? Is which wicked nigger curse they chile with a name like fookingal? Homer say. - Don't cross youself wid me woman. Me'd beat the piss out o' you. - Nobody beating no body in this kitchen. Say you piece then get out. -Paris. where him be? Four day gone and nobody no see him. - Anybody here look like Paris keeper?"</p>	<p>The words such as nigger , fookingal, pussyhole are racial slurs and insults that performs the act of wounding.</p>

<p>- Don't smart you mouth wid me , dry-up pussyhole." (James, 2009, p. 15)</p>	
<p>" You can't keep her forever, cow. Just watch when we get her. First we goin' to beat her face off. Then we goin' fuckout her cunt. Then we goin' kill her. Then we goin' fuck her again." (James,2009, p.16)</p>	<p>By sequencing beating, rape, killing and repeated rape, this articulates a script in which a woman's body is assigned a social role (punished, possessed, erased) and that role is made real by the very utterance.</p>
<p>"She cuss that they talk like negro folk and have poor breeding and smell bad. House niggers in the kitchen laugh cause they use to think only negro woman could smell bad"(James , 2009, p.25)</p>	<p>This show how injurious is internalised over time as black slaves had believe that only negro woman could smell.</p>
<p>"That instant between dreaming and waking she hear a whisper calling her the wickedest woman. A voice that trial off into the quiet. Paris didn't beat her or try to kill her and not even try to have his way with her, according to how the women describe it. Maybe she could have run 'way". (James, 2009, p.21)</p>	<p>This shows how injurious speech can be internalised over time. Lilith begins to believe herself evil because of what the other women says to her over time, reflecting how Injurious words can influence one's identity</p>
<p>" Make haste cow, he says" (James, 2009, p.10)</p>	<p>This an injurious speech that is meant to demean Lilith, to lessen herself worthwhile Paris tries to rape her.</p>
<p>Homer, Homer, Homer, have you been losing steps of late? Have you been slipping, you old cow" (James, 2009, p.20)</p>	<p>This is an injurious speech that is meant to remind Homer of her place as a worthless slave through demeaning words.</p>

Table 3: Subversive Resignification

EXCERPTS	DESCRIPTION
"That was the first time she feel the darkness. True darkness and woman that makes man scream" (James, 2009. P.11)	Here, a label once tied to fear and sin is redefined as a source of power and self-realisation.
"Then you is a real nigger for sure, - so when me can read chain goin' break? You is one perplexing nigger, Homer, anybody ever tell you? - Me not nobody nigger. Learn this, when you get can make out words, nothing the massa can do will surprise you" (James, 2009, p.39)	Homer takes the word "nigger," a term meant to degrade and control, and turns it into a site of resistance . Through her insistence on learning to read, she redefines what it means to be a Black enslaved person , not as powerless or ignorant, but as capable of intellectual and inner freedim
"Me will backtalk and front talk you, Negro" (James, 2009, p.41)	Black slaves in the text often use the word "negro" to refer to them selves. They reworked the term often use to degrade them by using it identity themselves.

Data Analysis

Gender Performativity in Marlon James' *The book of Night Women*

Judith Butler's notion of gender performativity posits that gender is not an innate identity but a repeated set of acts enforced through social norms and linguistic regulation (Butler, 1990). In *The Book of Night Women*, gendered identity is repeatedly produced through speech acts that discipline Lilith into a narrowly defined model of femininity.

The first excerpt in Table 1 clearly shows how gender is something people perform rather than something natural. In this scene, we see how those rules are taught and enforced from childhood. We see that process clearly through the wet nurse's speech and punishment. Lilith's behaviour, 'swing the club, clap the ball clear cross the field and make one run to all four base and beat the boys, shows her strength and confidence. These are qualities often linked with boys. By acting this way, Lilith steps outside what her society expects of a "good girl." Her physical prowess and competitiveness, traits culturally coded as masculine, constitute a performance that defies the expectations of femininity within the plantation world. This act

exposes the fact that gender is not natural but regulated, learned and enforced through language.

The wet nurse's reaction, "a good girl was supposed to make manchild win", shows how language acts as a tool of power in identity formation. Her words are not just describing what a girl should do; they are creating and enforcing that idea. In Butler's terms, this is a performative utterance, a kind of speech that does something. Here, the wet nurse's statement tries to mold Lilith into a submissive girl who helps boys succeed. Through this command, the wet nurse uses language to define what it means to be a "good girl." This act shows that identity is not something one simply has, but something that is spoken into existence by others and then repeated by the individual.

The second excerpt from table one explores the moment Lilith begins menstruation and deeply shows how identity is formed and controlled through language, especially through Circe's words and Lilith's silence. When Lilith's menstruation begins, her body signals a new stage of womanhood, yet she does not have the words to describe or understand it. Her inability to speak, "her mouth shut up and she couldn't do nothing but mumble", shows how language shapes identity by determining what can or cannot be said. Lilith's silence reflects that she has already learned shame through the words of others, especially Circe. In Butler's view, the power of language lies in how it can both name and wound, how being spoken to in certain ways fixes people within social meanings. Circe's sharp command, "Speak up, damn girl", illustrates this perfectly. The phrase is not simply an order to talk; it is a performative act that asserts Circe's authority and pushes Lilith into a position of submission. By addressing Lilith as "girl," Circe reinforces a specific identity: young, inferior, and needing correction. Through such language, Circe participates in the social process that defines what it means to be female and enslaved on the plantation.

Lilith's thought that "Circe would think she done nastiness for sure" reveals how Circe's earlier words have already taught her what her body supposedly means. Circe has often said that Lilith was "born to do nastiness with boy," which frames her female identity around sexual service and moral suspicion. Butler (1997) explains that repeated words and labels work like performances that build identity over time. Every time Circe speaks this way, she reinforces the idea that Lilith's body exists for male desire, and that her worth is measured by her sexual behaviour. Through Circe's speech, Lilith's transition into womanhood is immediately defined by sexual meaning rather than personal growth. Language becomes the medium that ties her identity to male control. She has not yet had a sexual experience, but the words spoken about her body already produce her as sexually available and morally corrupt. This shows how speech can imprison someone in a social identity they did not choose. In this moment, Circe's language becomes the medium through

which Lilith's identity as a "girl" and as a potential source of shame is produced. Lilith's silence shows how deeply language can control identity: even without speech, the social meanings placed upon her body are already internalised.

Similarly, the third excerpt further reflects how Circe's words construct Lilith's identity through language, shaping how others see her and how she is treated. Drawing on Judith Butler's (1997) *Excitable Speech*, we see that language does not merely describe a person, it produces their identity within systems of power. Circe's repeated description of Lilith as "too spirited" becomes a performative act that defines her identity and justifies violence against her. Circe's phrase "too spirited" is more than a judgement; it is a linguistic act of control. Through these words, Circe marks Lilith as a girl who resists the submissive role expected of enslaved women. The repetition of this label, "she too spirited, that damn girl" she need a man to fix her", turns Lilith's liveliness and independence into flaws. Butler (1997) explains that when speech is repeated within social hierarchies, it gains power to shape what is "real" or "true" about a person. In this way, Circe's language creates Lilith as a problem that must be corrected.

By saying that Lilith "need a man to fix her," Circe uses language to link gender identity to sexual domination. The phrase suggests that Lilith's female identity can only be controlled through the violence of a man. This reflects how, in the plantation world, femininity and blackness are defined through subjugation. Circe's words serve to justify sexual violence as a social tool to restore order. Butler's theory helps us see how this speech acts not only as insult but as a performative justification, words that make violence seem necessary or even natural. The statement "She is just a nigger girl" further reduces Lilith's identity to race and gender. This degrading label erases her individuality and fixes her within the lowest social position. Language here performs dehumanisation: it limits what Lilith can be, turning her into a stereotype rather than a person. Butler (1997) notes that when speech repeatedly names people within systems of inequality, it both wounds and constitutes them, producing subjects who are defined by oppression.

Thus, Circe's language functions as a weapon of both gender and racial power. By speaking about Lilith in this way, she participates in the creation of an identity that justifies exploitation. Lilith is constructed through Circe's words as a defiant girl who must be "broken", and this linguistic identity leads directly to physical violence. Yet the fact that Lilith kills her attacker can also be read as a refusal of that identity, a moment where she rejects what language tries to make her. Circe's words demonstrate how identity is formed and fixed through language. Her speech transforms Lilith's independence into a threat and her body into something that must be disciplined through male violence. Through Butler's lens, this scene shows that language on the plantation is not neutral, it is an instrument of power that shapes both how people are seen and how they come to see themselves.

Injurious Speech and the Power of Language in Identity Formation

The first excerpt from the second table shows how injurious language both wounds and forms identity, reflecting Judith Butler's (1997) idea that speech has power to constitute the subject it harms. The exchange between the Johnny Jumper and Homer is charged with violent, degrading language that does not merely express anger, it does violence through words.

The insults, "Move out of the way you sodomite", "dry-up pussyhole". are not random curses but performative acts of wounding. Each utterance attacks not only the listener's body but their sense of self. Butler explains that injurious speech names a person into a position within power relations; it creates a social reality in which the target is fixed as lesser. In calling Homer a "sodomite" or "pussyhole", the Johnny Jumper turns difference into disgrace, forcing the listener's identity to be defined through shame and violation. Such words mark Homer's body and voice as something that can be spoken over and controlled, showing how language makes subordination real.

The repetition of racial slurs, "nigger", "house nigger", deepens this wound. These words do not just describe social status; they enforce it. Through their repetition, the speaker re-creates the hierarchy of the plantation, where black identity is constantly tied to degradation. In this way, identity itself becomes a product of the violent speech that seeks to keep people in their "place". Butler (1997) argues that when people are named through hate speech, the name becomes part of them; it "sticks", shaping how they are seen and even how they come to see themselves. The Johnny Jumper's words, therefore, are acts of domination that wound Homer and, by extension, all who live under that language. Yet Homer's brief, witty replies, "which wicked nigger curse they child with a name like fookingal?" and "Nobody beating no body in this kitchen", reveal that language, while wounding, can also be a space of resistance. Her words momentarily unsettle the aggressor's authority. Even so, her need to defend herself through speech shows that her identity has already been forced into a position of threat and defence by the violence of language. In this scene, injurious speech is more than insult, it is a mechanism of identity formation. The Johnny Jumper's language constructs others as inferior, available to violence, and undeserving of respect. It turns hierarchy into habit, and humiliation into social order. Through Butler's lens, the scene shows how words do not simply wound; they form the identity of the wounded subject. The brutality of speech becomes the foundation on which identity, particularly racial and gendered identity, is produced and maintained within the world of the plantation.

Furthermore, the exchange in the second excerpt is a brutal example of how injurious speech wounds and, at the same time, produces identity. The threats are not merely violent promises; they are speech acts that enact a world in which Homer

already exists as an object to be violated. By naming Homer a “cow” and promising repeated degradation of the Lilith, the Junny jumper is not only promising harm but calling Lilith disposable, shameful and sexually available for domination. In Butlerian terms, these words perform the subject into a subordinated position: the utterance both injures and constitutes an identity defined by vulnerability and abjection. The repetition of the threats, beat, rape, kill, rape again, work linguistically to erase any claim Lilith might have to personhood. Each sentence reaffirms a social order where certain bodies (female, Black, enslaved) are publicly declared forfeitable; the language turns violence into an inevitable consequence of Lilith's supposed status. This is the productive cruelty of injurious speech: it binds bodily meaning to social station. To be called “cow” and to be named as the target of sexualised punishment is to be spoken into a state of utter social negation, and that spoken negation becomes part of how the community recognises her.

The sexual language here is specifically formative: by repeatedly tying Lilith's fate to sexual acts, the Johnny jumper reduces her identity to sexual availability and shame. The threat that rape will follow beating and death frames her body as a site of male entitlement, speech manufactures her as someone whose value is measured by what can be done to her sexually. Such rhetoric maps gender onto domination: womanhood, in this register, is legible only as subjection to male violence. Injurious language is revealed through how racial insult becomes internalised and turns into self-recognition. Mrs. Wilson's insult about “smelling bad” is not new to the enslaved women; it repeats a long history of racist speech that has defined Blackness as dirty, inferior, and subhuman. What is most striking, however, is that the Black women laugh because they once believed such words to be true. Their laughter is not simply amusement but a sign of how deeply language has shaped their sense of self. They had come to accept that “smelling bad” was an inherent trait of their race, proof that injurious speech has been absorbed into identity.

Judith Butler's theory of performativity helps to explain this process: identity is not fixed but is continually produced through repeated words and social acts. The repeated racial slurs, words like “negro” linked to dirt, smell, and lack of refinement, performatively construct the category of the Black woman as inherently unclean. Over time, these words cease to sound like external insults and start functioning as truths about who one is. The enslaved women's laughter therefore reveals how powerfully language operates to discipline the mind; they have been made to see themselves through the racist vocabulary of the oppressor. Mrs. Wilson's statement also exposes the hierarchy embedded in speech. When she says that the other white people “talk like negro folk”, her insult positions whiteness as purity and refinement, and Blackness as vulgarity and filth. The enslaved women's reaction confirms that the social order has succeeded in making its victims co-producers of that ideology. They recognise themselves in the insult, not because it

reflects truth, but because language has made it true within their lived world. Their laughter, then, is both a sign of internalisation and a faint, uneasy distance from it: they momentarily witness the absurdity of what they have been taught to believe. Thus, this scene demonstrates how language not only wounds but constructs racial identity. The repeated use of degrading descriptors has created a linguistic cage within which the enslaved women understand themselves. By internalising the idea that only “negro women could smell bad”, they illustrate how speech can colonise self-perception, transforming external abuse into internal belief, a clear example of how identity, especially under oppression, is shaped and maintained through the injurious power of words.

In the fourth excerpt, we see the deep psychological effect of injurious speech on Lilith’s sense of self. The “whisper” calling her “the wickedest woman” is not merely an external accusation; it has entered her consciousness and begun to define how she sees herself. Though Lilith kills Paris in defence of her body, because he tries to rape her, the repeated language of condemnation around her transforms her act of resistance into one of sin. What we witness here is the process through which language wounds by reshaping moral perception and internal identity. Judith Butler (1997) explains that injurious speech not only hurts but also constitutes the subject identity. The words spoken about Lilith, calling her “wicked”, “evil”, or “ungrateful”, performatively mark her as a transgressor against both gender and racial expectations. Within the plantation world, an enslaved woman’s body is socially constructed as the property of men, especially white and overseer figures. By killing Paris, Lilith rejects that imposed role, but language denies her the possibility of moral justification. The voices around her, especially those of the women who claim Paris “didn’t beat her or try to kill her”, repeat the master’s narrative and thereby discipline Lilith’s sense of right and wrong.

The “whisper” she hears in the half-conscious state symbolises how deeply these words have been internalised; they have become part of her own inner voice. Language has colonised her mind, so she questions her own truth, “Maybe she be the one that evil”. This moment of doubt shows how injurious speech can blur the line between victim and offender, making Lilith internalise guilt for an act of survival. Her self-condemnation is thus a linguistic injury: she adopts the oppressor’s discourse and turns it inward, shaping her identity as “evil” rather than as a woman resisting violence. Marlon James reveals how speech operates as a tool of domination even in silence. The community’s talk about Paris and Lilith reasserts patriarchal and racial hierarchies, ensuring that resistance is linguistically rewritten as wickedness. In absorbing this language, Lilith becomes both the subject and the victim of injurious speech, her identity fractured by words that define her moral worth through the lens of the oppressor

Subversive Resignification in *The book of Night Women*.

The first excerpt in Table 3 demonstrates subversive resignification, the process Judith Butler (1997) describes as the repetition of a word or practice originally used to oppress, but redeployed in a way that unsettles and reverses its injurious force. Lilith's awakening marks a pivotal moment of resignification, in which a label historically associated with fear and moral corruption is transformed into a source of power and self-recognition. The phrase "the darkness" has long functioned within the patriarchal and slaveholding order of *The Book of Night Women* as a marker of Blackness, and particularly Black womanhood as evil, savage, and dangerous. Within colonial discourse, darkness is synonymous with moral deficiency and racial inferiority. In this moment, however, Lilith reclaims "darkness," converting it from a term of condemnation into a symbol of agency and embodied strength. Butler's (1997) notion of subversive resignification explains how injurious terms can be repeated in ways that undo their original force. Lilith's "darkness" no longer signifies the racialised degradation imposed by white and patriarchal discourse; instead, it becomes an internal recognition of her capacity for action and resistance. The violent act itself—pouring boiling tea on Paris as he attempts to violate her—marks a decisive reversal of power. Lilith shifts from object to actor, from a body defined through others' language to a subject who asserts meaning through embodied action. Her "darkness" is thus re-signified as the core of a woman capable of making a man "scream," symbolising her rejection of submission and her reclamation of moral and physical autonomy.

What makes this act subversive is that Lilith does not discard the term "darkness" but reworks it. The word retains its intensity—it still evokes danger and fear—but its direction is inverted. What once served the logic of domination now serves her self-definition. This inversion disrupts the master's discourse by exposing its instability: the very term used to mark her inferiority becomes the language of her awakening. Through this resignification, Lilith destabilises colonial binaries such as purity versus corruption, good versus evil, and masculine dominance versus feminine passivity. Language and embodiment converge in this moment, as "darkness" becomes a language of her own making—a space in which an enslaved woman claims the authority to define what her Blackness and womanhood signify. By embracing the term that once constrained her identity, Lilith exposes its contingency and transforms it into a declaration of strength.

The second excerpt in Table Three further illustrates subversive resignification through linguistic contestation. The word "nigger," historically deployed as a tool of dehumanisation, becomes a site of struggle and redefinition between Lilith and Homer. When Homer states, "Then you are a real nigger for sure," she initially echoes the language of oppression. However, this repetition is strategic, preparing the ground for a reversal of meaning. In the exchange that follows, Homer

transforms the defining features associated with the term—ignorance, illiteracy, and submission—into possibilities for consciousness and resistance through literacy. Homer’s declaration, “Me not nobody nigger. Learn this, when you can make out words, nothing the massa can do will surprise you,” constitutes an act of linguistic rebellion. By rejecting the imposed identity encoded in the term “nigger,” she redefines herself as an epistemic agent. Language, here, becomes a medium of liberation rather than subjugation. Literacy, deliberately denied to enslaved people as a mechanism of control, is re-signified as a private and subversive form of power. When Homer asserts, “Every time you open this you set free, freeness up in here,” she reclaims the concept of freedom itself—historically restricted to whiteness—and internalises it as a mental and spiritual condition that exceeds physical bondage.

This exchange stages a struggle over meaning in which the master’s vocabulary is turned against him. The same linguistic system that defines “nigger” as inferior is reworked to reveal how knowledge destabilises that definition. Homer’s speech exemplifies the subversive potential Butler (1997) attributes to resignification: by repeating an oppressive term while altering its context and implication, she dislodges its authority. Her words do not merely describe freedom; they perform it. Identity and resistance are forged within the very language designed to suppress them. Through this interaction, both speech and subjectivity are re-signified: the derogatory label becomes a catalyst for critical awareness, reading becomes an act of defiance, and the enslaved subject emerges as self-defining through reinterpreted language. Homer teaches Lilith that the path to freedom begins in words—the same words once used to bind them—thus transforming linguistic injury into linguistic agency.

Discussion of Findings

This study set out to examine the relationship between language and identity in Marlon James’s *The Book of Night Women* through Judith Butler’s extension of Speech Act Theory, with particular attention to gender performativity, injurious speech, and subversive resignification. The findings reveal that language in the novel functions as a central mechanism through which identity, especially Black female subjectivity, is produced, regulated, wounded, and, at moments, resisted. In line with Butler’s (1990; 1997) arguments, the analysis demonstrates that identity in the plantation world is not pre-given but emerges through repeated speech acts embedded within asymmetrical relations of power.

One significant finding is that gender identity in the novel is constituted through continuous linguistic regulation. From early childhood, Lilith’s behaviour is monitored and corrected through speech that defines what it means to be a “good girl.” Commands, reprimands, and labels operate performatively, transforming social expectations into lived realities. As Butler (1990) argues, gender is not an

internal essence but an effect of repetition. In *The Book of Night Women*, femininity is repeatedly enacted through speech that privileges submission, sexual restraint, and self-effacement, while deviations from these norms are punished. Language thus becomes a disciplinary technology that produces gendered bodies aligned with plantation hierarchies.

The findings further show that injurious speech plays a constitutive role in shaping racialised and gendered identities. Racial slurs, sexualised insults, and threats of violence do not merely reflect oppression; they actively bring it into being. Consistent with Butler's (1997) notion of excitable speech, such utterances derive their force from historical repetition and institutional authority. Words like "nigger," "cow," and sexually degrading insults repeatedly position Black women as disposable, morally suspect, and sexually available. Through these speech acts, violence is normalised and legitimised, while the subjectivity of enslaved women is reduced to vulnerability and abjection.

Another crucial finding concerns the internalisation of injurious speech as the analysis demonstrates that repeated exposure to degrading language reshapes self-perception, leading characters to recognise themselves through the vocabulary of oppression. Moments where enslaved women laugh at racist insults or where Lilith hears condemning voices within her own consciousness illustrate Butler's argument that injurious speech wounds by becoming part of the subject's inner life. Language thus extends its power beyond immediate interaction, infiltrating thought, memory, and moral judgement. This internalisation ensures the durability of domination even in the absence of direct coercion. Despite the overwhelming force of linguistic domination, the study also reveals moments where language becomes a site of resistance through subversive resignification. Characters such as Lilith and Homer rework terms historically associated with degradation, such as "darkness" and "nigger" and invest them with new meanings. These acts of resignification do not erase the history of violence attached to the words; rather, they expose the instability of oppressive discourse. In Butler's (1997) terms, repetition is never perfect, and it is within this imperfection that resistance emerges.

Through recontextualisation, enslaved women reclaim agency, redefine selfhood, and articulate alternative forms of subjectivity within the very language that once confined them.

Overall, the findings confirm Butler's central claim that speech is both injurious and productive. In *The Book of Night Women*, language does not simply describe identity; it performs it. It produces gendered and racialised subjects aligned with plantation power structures while simultaneously carrying the potential to disrupt those structures. Identity in the novel is therefore shown to be a fragile, contested, and ongoing process shaped by linguistic struggle.

Conclusion

This study concludes that in *Book of Night The Women*, Marlon James illustrates Judith Butler's argument that language is not just used for expression ideas, but a tool for identity formation. Through Lilith's experiences, the novel shows how injurious speech, words of insult, command, and judgement, shapes identity by forcing the enslaved to internalise the oppressor's language. However, it also reveals the possibility of resistance through subversive resignification, where those same words are reinterpreted to express power, knowledge, and agency. Lilith's journey from silence to self-awareness demonstrates that identity is not fixed but performed through language.

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